

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B106
Date: 30 Jun 2005
Take Off: 10:51:25
Landing: 15:22:54
Flight Time: 4h31m29

Campaign: ICEPIC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Jonathan Smith	Leeds
5	Flight Manager	Stephen Devereau	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics/CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	CVI/CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	ADA / CPI	Martin Gallagher	Manchester University
9	Mission Scientist 2	Richard Cotton	Met Office
10	AMS / CCN training	Hugh Coe	Manchester University
11			
12			
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Flight Track:

B106 Track 30-JUN-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B106
 Date: 30th June 2005
 Project: ICEPIC
 Location: SW Approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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103115		INU to Nav			
105125		T/O	5.0 kft	268	
110431		J/W zeroed	9.8 kft	245	
112725		Fwd camera iced	18.0 kft	250	
113259		Fwd camera clear	18.0 kft	248	
114215	120504	Profile 1	18.0 - 5.4 kft	248	
115544		interrupt P1	5.4 kft	247	
120400	120932	Run 1.1	5.3 kft	247	
121255	121452	Run 1.2	7.3 kft	054	
121823	121952	Run 1.3	7.9 kft	230	
122305	122446	Run 1.4	8.2 - 8.1 kft	052	
122738	122946	Run 1.5	8.3 kft	253	
123321	123519	Run 1.6	8.4 kft	060	
123832	124013	Run 1.7	8.8 kft	316	
124314	124522	Run 1.8	8.8 kft	124	
130409	130524	Run 2.1	8.9 kft	077	
130850	131018	Run 2.2	8.9 - 9.0 kft	249	
131320	131501	Run 2.3	9.2 kft	078	
131757	131939	Run 2.4	9.5 kft	273	
132305	132434	Run 2.5	9.7 kft	084	
132738	132912	Run 2.6	9.9 kft	253	
133250	133439	Run 2.7	10.0 kft	035	
133742	133903	Run 2.8	10.0 kft	240	
134241	134419	Run 2.9	10.2 - 10.3 kft	048	
134800	134858	Run 2.10	9.8 kft	226	
135520	141831	Profile 2	11.0 - 0.50 kft	278	
135734		interrupt P2	9.0 kft	279	
135933		recommence P2	9.0 kft	063	
140519		interrupt P2	4.4 kft	052	
140845		recommence P2	4.3 kft	225	
141306		interrupt P2	2.1 kft	226	
141501		recommence P2	2.2 kft	039	
141842	142629	Run 3	0.58 - 0.61 kft	050	
142820	143622	Run 4	1.6 kft	057	
152254		Land	0.55 kft	356	

B106 Track 30-JUN-05

PROJECT BRIEF: ICEPIC – development of ice and precipitation in cumulus clouds.

Scientific Aims: The goal of ICEPIC is to understand and quantify the formation and growth of ice particles in cumulus clouds. We wish to examine:

- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

As a first priority, in-situ aerosol and microphysical measurements from the aircraft will be gathered in close coordination with the CAMRa radar at Chilbolton, Hants. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C. The radar may identify columns of supercooled raindrops within the growing cumulus clouds that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft.

Weather conditions: Developing showers that are forecast to have tops up to about -15°C within range of the Chilbolton radar. It may be preferable to fly to an alternative region away from the radar if conditions are more suitable.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. Information on current location of lightning (sferics) can be provided by FAAM using the NAMIS system. Several aircraft will be operating in the boundary layer at the same time as part of CSIP: UFAM Cessna - entire project; German DO-128 - 20 June to 17 July; NERC DO-228 - August. (The BAS Twin Otter may also participate in CSIP.)

Key instruments and their operation

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- FWVS
- GPS (including cruciform), INU, turbulence probe When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP (or CIP-100), PCASP, SID-1 (and *SID-2*). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, pristine ice crystal habits, large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery above freezing level.
- (ADA)/CPI as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator (2min reqd.) whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- *Ice Nucleus counter (INC) will normally be operated in clear air and under fixed conditions of temperature and supersaturation so as to maintain it in a stable condition. Allow additional time between runs for the operator to adjust it to different conditions.*
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. When straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS - min 2mins (~12km) reqd for size-resolved composition distribution.
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode

- above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode to sample cloud particle residues into the AMS.

SORTIE BRIEF: ICEPIC ICE and Precipitation Initiation in Cumulus clouds

Flight Number: B106

Date: 30th June 2005

Mission Scientist: Jonathan Smith

Sortie Aims: To measure development of microphysics and dynamics in cumulus cloud systems.

Location: Amongst developing cumulus clouds within 1-5 hours transit of Cranfield. Areas Alpha and Echo, with preference be to west of Chilbolton radar facility (to be within radar range).

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise inflow atmosphere around and below developing cumulus – *where not done by CSIP*
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds, preferably near the top of growing turrets, through the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be *with wings level*. Three principal options are for:
 - A well-defined isolated clouds
 - B many clouds (RICO scenario)
 - C organised convection on a convergence line or a gust front.

Meteorological information will be given from the CSIP Operations Centre at Chilbolton before flight and in-flight (using VHF radio, new frequency is 130.575 MHz, call-sign remains “Radsearch”).

Sortie Detail

1. Out-of-Cloud: only where not done by CSIP

- 1.1. Take off and climb for transit to the operating area. Locate suitable growing cumulus. 40+ min
- 1.2. *Optional profile descent in clear air, 1000 ft/min, FL200 to 500 ft agl. If necessary step profile to stay in area. (Not required at Chilbolton) Set altitudes and directions for later[†].* 25 min
- 1.3. Run at 500 ft agl, minimum length 50 km along suitable azimuth (across line or front for Option C) to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require initial delay to settle instruments. 10 min
- 1.4. Ascend to 500 ft below cloud base and carry out 50 km run on suitable azimuth to sample inflow aerosols & IN. May require delay after ascent to settle instruments. 15 min

2. Cloud Work Options

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with clouds, near their top

- A.1. Proceed to about 0° C altitude[†], or below max cloud top if lower 5 min
- A.2. Adjust altitude to 500 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude. It is important to penetrate the growing turret, updraught, region. Once clear of cloud, continue run for 10 s then procedure turn to return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible. 5 min
- A.3. As time permits, repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) until T = -20° C[†].
{ Vertical separation of repeats set to match growth of cloud} 45 min

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample many clouds

- B.1. Proceed to 0° C altitude[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- B.2. Commence 10 min run in along shear direction[†]. Adjust track to randomly sample growing turret / updraught regions of cloud but without passing through RED radar echoes (reflectivities of 37 dBZ or greater). End run clear of cloud. 10 min
- B.3. As time permits, repeat an ascent by -3° C[†] (approximately 1500 ft) followed by a run as in B.2 until the lowest of -15° C[†] or max cloud top is reached. (-3, -6, -9, -12, -15° C[†]) 75 min

Option C: Clouds with linear organization (eg. along a convergence line or gust front).

- C.1. Proceed to 0° C[†], or max cloud top if lower 5 min
- C.2. Fly leg perpendicular to line, length as required. Adjust track to penetrate cloud tops or cell centres. End run clear of cloud. 2 min
- C.3. As time permits, repeat a 180° turn and ascent followed by C.2. Ascent either; as A to 500 ft below cloud tops until -20° C[†] reached, or as B at fixed temperature levels. 30+ min

3. Repeat If time permits, for new developing cumulus carry out Option A, B or C.

Transit return at any suitable altitude. 40+ min

Mission Scientist's Log

Jonathan Smith

Flight No **B.106**.....

Date **30th June '03**.....

Page **1** of **3**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:49	t/o				8/8 Cu
10:50	climb out	1600ft			close, visibility good
10:52	trim	5000ft			7/8 Cu 3/8 Ci - outside T ~ 11°C slight inst.
11:02	climb in-trim	5300	264	52.0/1.6W	cu - main top level, a few higher
		0°C at 725 hPa or approx. 9000 ft			→ this side (East) of system
11:25:06	trim	FL180	250	51.5N/1.2W	now in cloud, before had 9/8 (2000) Ci band
11:31	"	"			1/8 ^{above} Cs, 7/8 Sc, 1/8 As
11:42:15	P1 str		248		
11:44	↑ ↓	16,000			-15
					-12 ~ 580 hPa
		13,500			-10
					-9 ~ 620 hPa
		11,800			-6
11:52		8,700			-3 2/8 As 2/8 Cu 2/8 Sc
	6700			0 670 hPa 775 say 6,500 as target	
11:57	hold on P1 str	5300ft	246		+3°C
11:59		good cloud ahead			- into Irish air space
		ship B splits A part 1			
12:07					into cloud, but bumpy & a bit low
		some As on other side in			As ahead + done behind
					13:15 205
12:18	drop 200 ft				seemed level than drop 30
					"

12:19:30 → hole in middle
 " 17:59 - into
 18:35

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.106**

Date **30th June '03**

Page **2** of **3**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					2D - large drops on run
13:20					SID 50% is non-spherical
	R1-h				FO - 8°C
					in "h" → ".15" out ~ 30s
	As layer still around the				cu
	near top				~ 5s more at T - 1.5°C
		8100			T - 1.6h next
	v.				As above stand of run
	looks like two tunnels in there				
	time through it is				
12:42:21					Last run → nearer top than time before
					∴ will now repeat at same altitude
12:43:14		8200			cloud to rear has built up
	large area has stopped				"08" into cloud & out
13:02 →	new cloud				popped thro' immersion layer
	(one to South)				
13:04	'39' into				'02' out 24s
13:08	bit high ∴ drop down				(some cloud before start)
	T = -2.				'29.5" into cloud 58" out 30s
13:13	same tunnel now				
13:14:50 →	25s				through the cloud
	different tunnel - slightly bigger than others				
13:19:14	into tunnel				18s through it picture
	of new tunnel on nose & old one on				

part now 2D 3mm drops seen

19-256

ETA
cranfield
16:20 local

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....106.....

Date 30th June '05.....

Page 3 of 3.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:28					up still (keep going) hwy
				17s	through cloud
13:33		1000			too high ~
					tops die down cd nothing re-appears - have to come down on altitude
					did it stop for small immersion or did spready
14:03 or so					picture of similar clouds, but not the same as we worked, they are behind us.
					edge of boundary layer cu - picture taken earlier 14:20 of what happened - small cu grows either meets or spreads out as Sc
14:22:13					sea state at best 1/10 white water
14:25:29		small boat	B		
14:30:18		small boats	again		2/8 Cu above, rming below base hazy, 1/8 As, 3/8 Ci above
14:33					more Ci 2/8 now at this end of
14:35	R4	1500	59	51.0N/54W	the run
					definite change at end of run
15:02:06	transit return				picture of screen for timecheck (in cloud)

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	65	108	110
POST FLIGHT	57	104	110

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.3	0.35	1.109	0.069	0.000 initially 0.466 after reboot
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
Synced @ 09:01:37	33.79	1.18	7.11	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1 (sample A)	-1 (sample B)	-1 (sample B)	0 (sample B)	0 (sample A)	-1 (sample A)	
NO (ppbV)	0.5	0.52	0.55	0.62	0.61	0.59	0.565
NO₂ (ppbV)	0.35	0.38	0.29	0.20	0.20	0.32	0.29
NO_x (ppbV)	0.85	0.9	0.84	0.82	0.81	0.91	0.855
SO₂ (ppbV)	-3.90	-4.28	-3.44	-3.24	-3.13	-3.22	-3.535

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

O₃ clicking sound from instrument as sample changes from B to A. Not noticed this before. Dull, soft thud as switched from A to B..

SO₂ flow was zero initially. Rebooted @ 08:05 after which it was OK (0.466)

SO₂ Lamp Intensity was low (varying between 12500Hz & 16000Hz. Min is set to 16000Hz.

SO₂ Lamp voltage was high (1362V @ 09:58). Intensity had increased by this point though still occasionally dipping low.

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	29 Jun 2005 14:32:23 Ground (refuel stop @ Newcastle)	78.30	94.84	7425.53

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)
08:03:01 (1 st auto cal)	Ground (pre flight) (405-415)	64.79	89.19	5778.44	34.10	7.16	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.04	0.3	0.35	1.109	0.069	-
Time	Flight Level	CO					
08:35:53	Ground (648-652)	78.76	92.86	7313.13	50	7.15	33.95
Time	Flight Level	CO					
09:08:45	ground ()	77.31	95.41	7375.66	50	7.12	33.89
Time	Flight Level	CO					
09:41:37	ground (499-506)	75.14	96.93	7283.51			
Time	Flight Level	CO					
Unmanned auto cals in flight.		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
15:01:51	?? transit ()	81.14	91.02	7385.70			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS
Nil

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B106

Date: 30/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 1 of 1

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
11:42:15	29	0.08	1	30	33	525	8	6025	800	8	Start P1 Descent @ FL180
11:43:28	30	0.09	1	3	0.5	200	8	91	200	8	170
11:44:31	39	0.12	1	30	2	100	10	8	200	10	160
11:45:37	50	0.08	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	150
11:46:49	45	0.08	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	140
11:47:51	50	0.08	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	130
11:48:58	80	0.09	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	120
11:49:58	110	0.1	1	0	0	0	0	00	0	0	110
11:51:01	322	0.12	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
11:52:07	114	0.09	1	10	1	750	8	425	800	8	90
11:53:07	118	0.09	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
11:54:06	171	0.09	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70
11:55:03	159	0.08	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60
11:55:44	212	0.09	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	5300ft P1 interrupt
											P1 restart @ 5300ft
											Profile cancelled
12:	Run never	called	Low conc	approx	100 on 2dc	large	water	droplets			Start run 1 in cloud @ 5300ft
											End run 1
											FFSSP restarted - not responding
12:12:55	19	0.08	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 2 @ 7300ft
12:14:00	376	0.47	23	3000	431	450	1	5541	400	1	In cloud
12:14:51	29	0.09	88	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End of run 2
12:18:24	38	0.09	88	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 3 @ 7800ft
12:19:00	185	0.28	95	3000	300	400	1	2999	3000	1	In cloud
12:19:52	35	0.09	145	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 3
12:23:04	38	0.09	145	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 4 @ 8100ft
12:23:50	32	0.3	147	3000	277	250	1	441	200	1	In cloud
12:24:30	16	0.09	174	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 4

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B106

Date: 30/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 2 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
12:27:38	28	0.09	174	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 5 @ 8300ft
12:29:05	1000	0.5	192	3000	500	200	1	No	Time		In cloud
12:29:20	14	0.1	193	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	end run 5
12:33:21	12	0.09	197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 6 @ 8500ft
12:34:40	45	0.1	198	100	4.5	75	1	33	0	0	In cloud
12:35:19	15	0.09	199	0	0	0	0	0	0		End run 6
12:38:31	9	0.08	199	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 7 @ 8800ft
12:39:20	17	0.6	203	3000	0	0	0	41.6	N/a	N/a	In cloud
12:40:16	9	0.08	216	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 7
12:43:13	6	0.09	216	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 8 @ 8800ft
12:44:10	11	0.57	220	3000	0	0	0	208	N/a	N/a	In cloud
12:45:20	5	0.08	226	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 8
13:04:10	8	0.07	232	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 9 @ 8900ft
13:04:43	500	0.6	252	3000	288	650	1	1842	800	1	In Cloud
13:05:21	16	0.09	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 9
13:08:50	21	0.2	305	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 10 @ 8900ft
13:09:34	1366	0.75	321	3000	411	225	1	1175	200	1	In Cloud
13:10:17	14	0.09	366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End Run 10
13:13:21	4	0.07	366	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 11 @ 9200ft
13:14:19	52	0.4	376	3000	400	225	1	2616	600	1	In Cloud
13:15:20	13	0.08	430	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End Run 11
13:17:56	7	0.08	430	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 12 @ 9700ft
13:19:07	723	0.6	455	3000	378	800	1	3291	3000	1	In Cloud
13:19:39	11	0.07	496	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 12

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B106

Date: 30/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 3 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:23:04	10	0.07	496	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 13 @ 9700ft
13:24:05	500	0.7	515	3000	500	200	1	1000	400	1	In Cloud
13:24:15	5	0.09	525	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End Run 13
13:27:38	13	0.08	525	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 14 @ 9700ft
13:28:35	500	0.7	544	3000	300	275	1	1000	200	1	In Cloud
13:29:12	12	0.08	567	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 14
13:32:50	10	0.08	567	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 15 @ 10000ft
13:34:39	500	0.2	Missed	Turret							End run
13:37:42	10	0.08	569	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 16 @ 1000ft
13:38:24	1000	0.7	593	3000	240	800	1	240	1200	1	In Cloud
13:38:08	4	0.07	593	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	End run 16
13:42:40	20	0.07	593	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 17 @ 10200ft
13:43:50	400	0.7	613	3000	1200	150	1	800	missed	1	In Cloud
13:44:19	7	0.08	613	0	0	0	0	0	0		End run
13:47:02	9	0.08	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start run 18 @ 9700ft
13:48:58	Missed	Turret									In Cloud
											End run 18
13:55:20	13	0.08	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	P2 @ FL110
13:56:17	7	0.08	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100
13:57:34	5	0.08	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	90 P2interrupted
13:59:34	3	0.07	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	90 P2 restarted
14:00:35	15	0.09	613	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	80
14:01:31	43	0.09	613	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70
14:02:31	185	0.1	613	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	60
14:03:49	225	0.1	613	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	50
14:05:19	176	0.1	613	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	4400ft P2 interrupted

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B106**

Date: 30/06/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B106

Date: 30/06/05

Instruments

1. Video – DFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off . Also, RFC (marked DFC...) is virtually black on pc monitor, whereas it displays well on video monitor unit.
2. CVI – butanol in exhaust pipe
3. CVI – AMS after 7000ft flow stopped and started sucking butanol into plenum from 3010, meaning AMS being contaminated with butanol.

Aircraft

Satcom H:-

